

Rac-5d

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-185-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	92	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 185 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/6/2021 9:46:53 PM CST		
Date Processed:	12/7/2021 2:37:36 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.597	6958240	50.34	244832
2	21.515	6863471	49.66	159736

Asy-5d

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-19-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	1207
Vial:	10	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 19
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/7/2021 11:45:48 AM CST		
Date Processed:	12/7/2021 2:39:32 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.547	16135648	98.01	566359
2	21.495	326836	1.99	8127